

DEVELOPMENT OF AN EFFERVESCENT TABLET FORM FOR BATHS WITH SOOTHING AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECT BASED ON NATURAL RAW MATERIALS

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Relevance: In recent decades, there has been a steady increase in the incidence of skin pathologies — allergic dermatitis, eczema, psoriasis, as well as various forms of skin irritation caused by adverse environmental conditions, stress, and reduced immunity. According to dermatological practice, up to 20–30% of the population of different age groups experience manifestations of skin hypersensitivity, accompanied by itching, inflammation, and impaired barrier function. Existing dosage forms (ointments, alcohol-based solutions, creams) have limitations: they may cause burning and discomfort, make it difficult to apply evenly over large skin areas, and reduce treatment adherence. In this regard, there is growing interest in remedies based on natural plant and mineral raw materials, which are characterized by mild action, ecological safety, and ease of use.

Objective: To develop an effervescent tablet form for baths, providing soothing, anti-inflammatory, and softening effects for sensitive skin.

Materials and Methods: The active components included licorice extract, oat powder, sea salt, kaolin, and lavender essential oil. The effervescent base consisted of citric acid and sodium bicarbonate, while starch and sorbitol were used as excipients. Laboratory studies were carried out to select the optimal ratio of acid and bicarbonate, which showed that upon tablet dissolution, the reaction proceeded completely, and the resulting solution had a pH of 6.5–7.0, corresponding to the physiological level of the skin. This confirmed the absence of irritating effects on damaged areas. Additionally, organoleptic properties, dissolution rate, and stability of the obtained tablets were evaluated. The results demonstrated that all included ingredients are not only safe but also possess beneficial dermatoprotective properties: reducing itching and inflammation, promoting hydration, and providing gentle skin cleansing.

Results: Laboratory tests established that the effervescent base (citric acid and sodium bicarbonate) at the optimal ratio is fully neutralized, producing a solution with pH 6.5–7.0, safe for damaged skin. The active components (licorice, oats, sea salt, kaolin, lavender) confirmed their dermatoprotective properties: relieving itching, reducing inflammation, gentle cleansing, and skin mineralization. The developed form demonstrated safety, stability, and promising potential as a preventive skincare product.

Conclusion: The development of effervescent bath tablets based on natural raw materials represents a promising direction in pharmaceutical technology. The product may be used for prevention and comprehensive care in cases of allergies, dermatitis, and skin hypersensitivity across different age groups.